

UNIVERSITY OF
BUCHAREST
VIRTUTE ET SAPIENTIA

**WHY MICRO-CREDENTIALS SHOULD BECOME
EDUCATIONAL “MACRO-POLICIES”
FOR DEFINING THE FUTURE
EUROPEAN STUDY PROGRAMMES**

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1. „ Universities without walls” or the path towards the new European curriculum

The idea expressed by Michael Murphy, the current President of the European University Association (EUA), of shaping the vision of the evolution of higher education in the next decade in relation with the metaphor “universities without walls” (EUA, 2020a), evoked several times especially because of its implications, raises a genuine question of philosophy, of attitude and approach.

Up until the beginning of last year, in 2020, some of our preconceptions concerning the future of European universities had a conservative undertone, but they have been entirely swept away by the new challenges posed by the Covid pandemic, that the leadership and academic communities have had to address. Although it has suddenly accelerated the digitalization of higher education institutions, the pandemic has also brought about some more profound structural changes benefitting students, related to academic teaching and learning processes, allowing for a more inclusive and flexible approach when it comes to learning.

From a certain perspective, the fundamental preconditions underlying the launch of the “European Universities” project were related to sound principles of structural public policy. These principles took into account the students’ need for growth and training, and were based on a set of visionary ideas on changing the learning environments and strategies, providing more inclusiveness and flexible learning in Europe’s near future. However, in order to change learning environments, it is necessary not only to have well-prepared teachers, inspired by innovative pedagogies (a genuine need highlighted in European documents at the moment when the initiative was launched), but also to reconsider the academic curriculum (Debiais-Sainton & Karamali, 2020):

- A flexible and customized European curriculum, with embedded mobility, leading to a European Degree;
- Innovative pedagogies with a challenge-based transdisciplinary approach.

At the same time, it is important to mention that this strategic context of change is based on respecting the continuity of higher education policy processes, by upholding the Bologna Process Key Commitments.

Flexible and open learning paths, part of the original inspiration for the Bologna Process, are important aspects of student-centred learning and are in increasing demand in our societies. In addition to full degree programmes, many higher education institutions offer or plan to offer smaller units of learning, which enable learners to develop or update their cultural, professional, and transversal skills and competences at various stages in their lives. We ask the BFUG to explore how and to what extent these smaller, flexible units, including those leading to micro-credentials, can be defined, developed, implemented, and recognised by our institutions using EHEA tools. (EHEA, 2020, p. 6)

However, from the perspective of the beneficiaries and of their future, the most important premise out of all of these is the one referring to the flexible and customized European curriculum, leading to a European Degree; this easily becomes clear, directly, through the voice of the students from the European Students' Union (ESU): "One of the key cooperation principles of alliances indicates that students can design their own flexible curricula, leading to a European Degree. ESU here sees a lack of common understanding to what is a European Degree" (ESU, 2020). This statement confirms the expectations related to a new understanding of the relation between European certifications and a ***flexible and customized European curriculum***.

In addition to these arguments, coming from students' organizations, there are also arguments coming from the public sphere, from the employers' side. These actors are interested in more relevance, in a focus on trans-disciplinarity when it comes to academic qualifications, in versatility, variety and flexibility, not necessarily for organizing learning, but rather to put to good use the products of academic learning, the competencies, skills and attitudes, in European professional environments, defined by dynamism and unpredictability.

Therefore, this shift in the academic paradigm cannot be only structural, but rather it will have to rely on a new philosophy, on a new way of building the academic curriculum, closer to the belief in a future of "**universities without walls**", where the "walls" can be understood as the limitations of the traditional academic curricular framework.

Thus, the challenge of such a curricular construction with which European Alliances are faced cannot be based merely on a conversion of the current national academic curriculum (accredited in accordance with the national quality assurance standards) and on adding the designation "European" to the already existing qualification, launching it under the auspices of a European Alliance. The most important part of the new philosophy is related to the ***principle of a flexible and customized European curriculum***, which will probably raise most contradictions when it comes to construction. This new paradigm requires that certain phrases, such as: modular design, micro-credentials, micro-programmes, flexible learning pathways, gradually accompany the traditional educational-pedagogical terminologies of structures that lead, in a linear and passive way, to obtaining an academic qualification.

Becoming aware of this need for change will put pressure on education institutions that are members of the European Alliances, and others. In this context, we are wondering if within the European Alliances launched so far one can notice a preoccupation with the new priorities related to redesigning the curriculum, which is vital for the architecture of the future academic offering of those legal entities which will be created once these large-scale projects are completed. A brief analysis, carried out by mapping synthetic applications uploaded on official sites, provides evidence showing that these changing processes are marginal or are understood as processes through which the new certifications are cumulative products of the existing ones, launched, in a best-case scenario, as academic experiences resembling "joint degrees" (joint study programmes).

The European future, also marked by the current health crisis, will bring about increased pressure on the new institutions, given the public need not only to give up own institutional walls, but also to redesign the new customized European academic curriculum by means of flexibility, modularization, micro-credentials and recognition up to the level of non-formal competencies; the ***new customized European academic curriculum***, a curriculum without walls, open to civic opportunities, and also to more inclusiveness and flexible learning in the European society in the near future.

2. The European vision on micro-credentials and their role in defining new specialisations

The changing nature of the European labour market and the increased uncertainty when it comes to professional stability place us in the situation of pondering on the question of how occupations will look like in the future. It is not new that more and more flexibility is required, and there is a need for rapid reactions when confronted with unpredictable circumstances. If we analyse the use of micro-credentials in direct relation with the effects of the current health crisis and with the labour market, we will notice that they hold the possibility of offering actors from the field of education and training a rapid and customized alternative for reprofessionalisation and skills learning.

The use of micro-credentials by higher education providers has the potential to foster continuous learning, fill the knowledge and skills gap, increase the efficiency of the higher education system, encourage innovation of provision, and reach a diverse group of learners. (BFUG, 2020, p. 1)

On September 30, 2020, the European Commission presented its vision regarding the future of the European Education Area by 2025¹, based on six key dimensions. In this sense, introducing micro-credentials in the higher education system is directly linked to the second dimension and constitutes a priority. Moreover, the new European Skills Agenda, launched on July 1st, 2020², provides that one of the 12 key actions is focused on the stringent need for higher education institutions in Europe to adopt micro-credentials.

The Commission will work towards the development of a European Approach to micro-credentials, to help widen learning opportunities and strengthen the role of higher education and vocational education and training institutions in lifelong learning by providing more flexible and modular learning opportunities. (Orr, Pupinis, & Kirdulytė, 2020, pp. 8-9)

¹ https://ec.europa.eu/education/sites/default/files/document-library-docs/eea-communication-sept2020_en.pdf

² https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/IP_20_1196

Of course, adopting micro-credentials is not an easy initiative, but the long-term benefits are sizeable enough so that the encountered challenges will not become obstacles and bottlenecks for an integrating system. Moreover, the analysis carried out by the Commission identified a series of challenges that may arise in the process of including micro-credentials in European educational systems (Orr, Pupinis, & Kirdulytė, 2020, p. 9):

- The complexity of micro-credentials and of their offering;
- The lack of understanding of what micro-credentials actually are;
- The lack of trust in certain micro-credentials;
- Limitations in the recognition and quality assurance of micro-credentials.

Just as these elements are being presented at a European level, we believe that the successful adoption of micro-credentials in higher education institutions largely depends on the impact which micro-credentials can have in the medium and long term. The micro-credentials system could potentially support and complete existing academic educational pathways, in that they provide increased trust in certification alternatives, improved transparency of learning results, educational innovation (especially when it comes to virtual mobility and innovative pedagogies) and flexibility in having students design educational programmes.

An investigative work aiming to provide the most appropriate and complete educational policy analyses when it comes to modularisation and micro-credentials in the European higher education (MicroHE Consortium, 2019, p. 36) identifies a series of expectations regarding the adoption of micro-credentials by European higher education institutions, divided in four categories and summarized by means of key words (see Figure 1).

Students	HEIs	Employers	Regulators
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Quality-driven</i> • <i>Updated</i> • <i>Accessible</i> 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Efficient</i> • <i>Reliable</i> • <i>Less bureaucratic</i> 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Flexible</i> • <i>Focused</i> • <i>Clear</i> 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Standardized</i> • <i>Employability-driven</i> • <i>Integrated</i>

Figure 1. Emerging expectations regarding the future of micro-credentials in higher education

The current European initiatives on micro-credentials are growing more and more, given that the need to adopt these new qualification forms is becoming more and more clear. As previously seen, one of the identified challenges in the process of adopting micro-credentials is precisely understanding these mechanisms and granting a clear and well-operationalised significance.

Although there are several definitions of micro-credentials, a consensus determining a unitary understanding across the European area has not been reached so far. In most cases, these definitions focus both on the learning activity leading to micro-credentials, and to the qualification itself.

Some definitions, such as the one included in an OECD working document (Kato et al., 2020, p. 8), draw a comparison between micro-credentials and traditional, standalone qualifications, stating that micro-credentials are “credentials that are not recognised as standalone formal educational qualifications”. The MicroHE project is based on the idea that micro-credentials are “sub-units of a credential that could accumulate into a larger credential or degree or be part of a portfolio” (MicroHE Consortium, 2019, p. 12).

Aiming to provide a definition of micro-credentials that is as complex and complete as possible, also tapping to a certain extent into its previous experience of defining them, the MICROBOL project adopted a working definition meant to support this broad-scale initiative of building a definition that is appropriate for the adequate understanding of micro-credentials.

A micro-credential is a small volume of learning certified by a credential. In the EHEA context, it can be offered by higher education institutions or recognised by them using recognition procedures in line with the Lisbon Recognition Convention or recognition of prior learning, where applicable. A micro-credential is designed to provide the learner with specific knowledge, skills or competences that respond to societal, personal, cultural, or labour market needs. Micro-credentials have explicitly defined learning outcomes at a QF-EHEA/NQF level, an indication of associated workload in ECTS credits, assessment methods and criteria, and are subject to quality assurance in line with the ESG. (EUA, 2020a, p. 7)

If we analyse the above definition, we will notice that it considers seven major components (see Figure 2) which define micro-credentials, thus providing a first conceptual framework for the future operationalisation of these new certification methods. Moreover, by analysing the components we notice that the understanding and adoption of micro-credentials by the higher education system is no longer entirely a strenuous process, but rather an initiative that can be accelerated by tapping into the rich experience of building study programmes at the level of higher education providers in Europe and elsewhere.

To facilitate the understanding of micro-credentials and the possibility of their adoption by higher education systems, a set of crucial data must be correlated with these certification mechanisms, in an effort to support the creation of a European micro-credentials framework. By designing clear and relevant components for academic educational endeavours, the reliability and transparency of micro-credentials can be ensured, from the perspective of both the academic world, and employers and civil society.

Figure 2. Components of micro-credentials

The European Commission study (Orr, Pupinis, & Kirdulytė, 2020, p. 14) on the relationship between micro-credentials and higher education in Europe identifies a set of 15 elements as being fundamental to a coherent functioning of micro-credentials across Europe.

- **Title of the micro-credential**, which precisely signals the learning outcomes
- **Provider of the course**
- **Date** when the micro-credential was awarded
- **Description** of the course content and its purpose
- **Learning outcomes** what the successful learner knows, understands, and can do based on this assessed learning
- **How the learner has participated** online, on-site, or both online and on-site
- **Credits** number of credits provided, if credit-bearing
- **Time period** when the learning took place
- **Any prerequisites** that were required to begin the course
- **Learning resources** relevant for the credential
- **Type of assessment** testing, application of a skill, portfolio, etc.
- **Supervision and identity verification** unsupervised with no identity verification, supervised with no identity verification, supervised online, or on-site with identity verification
- **Quality assurance** the body ensuring the quality of the course

- *Outcome for a successful learner admission to a degree programme, credit towards a degree programme, certification or digital badge earned, number of credits*
- *Integration / stackability options standalone, independent course / integrated, stackable towards another credential*

The adoption of micro-credentials by European higher education systems does not represent an initiative which decision-makers are not directly involved in, but for this process to occur on a large scale, we should identify several directions that can paint a picture of the overall European context. Thus, to ensure that the adoption of micro-credentials and micro-certifications has a high chance of success, we can highlight several issues that must be addressed as part of the effort of building the relevant EU-wide frameworks:

- As shown above, micro-credentials should be accompanied by clear and well-defined descriptive information;
- The information which defines the micro-credential should not be too strictly standardized or prescribed, so as not to straitjacket the educational process;
- It is necessary to set up a digital instrument to stock and ensure the portability of micro-credentials across the EU.
- The quality assurance process must be updated so as to meet the specific needs arising out of the adoption of micro-credentials.
- It is necessary to enhance the partnership between higher education institutions and actors in the world of work, with a view to identifying the most suitable training methods.

3. Why the Romanian system needs micro-credentials to participate in the European future of the academic curriculum

We can begin answering this more or less rhetorical question by referring to a study by Anthony F. Camilleri (2021). The study’s perspective is grounded in an analysis model of potential scenarios concerning the relationship between higher education and micro-credentials.

In this connection, starting from the idea that “it is ECTS rather than qualifications that should serve as a yardstick for learning” (Camilleri, 2018), and on the basis of three scenarios involving different degrees of adoption of micro-credentials by higher education institutions (Sood et al., 2020, pp. 22-43), from minimal to large-scale, Camilleri (2021) identifies six scenarios describing the positions that universities may take when faced with the challenge of micro-credentials. We will go over these scenarios below.

Scenario 1. Global micro-credentials marketplace

- Higher education institutions will cease to be the main providers of educational services and the main facilitators of the acquisition of the specific competences and skills required of professionals in a particular area.
- A broad category of private-sector providers together with several newly established structures resulting from a process of consortium-forming (which may lead to the emergence of 'mega-universities'), alongside other regional players, will dominate the market for this type of training programmes.
- Certain platforms, which will act as 'aggregators' on this market, will be able to provide their own training content, sharing market sections with universities and providers.

Scenario 2. European Universities

- European University Alliances will be able to provide specialised academic / professional content, in various languages of international communication, by using micro-credentials to offer 'joint flexible credentials', thus allowing students the freedom and flexibility to mix courses from the curriculum jointly agreed at the level of the alliances.
- All these academic learning and training experiences will be recognised by higher education institutions as well as employers on the European labour market.
- European University Alliances will become preferred learning paths for the acquisition of certain European and international qualifications, characterised by highly specialised and highly regarded occupational frameworks.

Scenario 3. Lifelong micro-learning

- The boundary between higher education and continuing vocational training becomes increasingly blurred in terms of credentials, with the emergence of certain entities that bring both educational aspects together into common processes.
- Individuals, which are increasingly seen as lifelong learners, juggle between the two education and training systems, and gradually turn into citizens who are 'engaged in perpetual learning'.
- Higher education institutions pay increasing attention to employee life cycles, with a view to implementing multiannual learning contracts with employers and students.

Scenario 4. University gatekeepers

- Universities are perceived as 'guarantors of quality', as they are authorised to award academic qualifications, thus serving as the cornerstone of the emerging institutional architecture.
- Institutional prestige becomes the guarantee for the quality of credentials, ensuring that the credential awarded meets the highest academic and professional standards.
- Universities become hubs for the array of training programmes put together by actors in the world of work, non-governmental organisations, or international organisations.

Scenario 5. Ivory towers

- Universities fail to acknowledge the role and growing significance of micro-credentials, ignoring technological and professional developments in the area of open education and the externalisation of education.
- Although universities continue to be the primary choice for certain areas, they are avoided when it comes to obtaining certain highly placed positions or professional roles, as career paths become fragmented and highly individualised.

Scenario 6. Outsourcing higher education

- Micro-credentials are tools of marginal significance to European students, who opt for traditional educational pathways at the expense of micro-credentials.
- Educational institutions can put together an attractive offer of micro-study programmes and micro-credentials for developing countries, whereby content will not only be provided to students, but will be licensed out to countries / whole systems (sale of licence agreements / educational copyrights to institutions in developing countries).
- European universities become leading higher education providers in developing countries, replacing local and national capacities, through effective campaigns and well-targeted offers.

To apply the study’s observations to the Romanian educational system, we have looked at each scenario in turn, while structurally and functionally adapting to the national context those scenarios which were deemed to possess the highest degree of feasibility and sustainability, considering the specificities of the Romanian university system, and given the regulatory framework in the area of qualifications and quality assurance of academic programmes. At the same time, the analysis highlights the specific situations in which a scenario may come to provide a genuine opportunity to help support a clearly articulated and coherent project aiming to integrate micro-credentials into the creation of the future *flexible learning pathways*.

On grounds of rational analysis, we have ruled out **Scenario 5**, metaphorically described as the *ivory tower*, as we believe Romanian universities could never follow a trajectory which is defined by a total rejection of the idea of utilizing and integrating micro-credentials within the academic curriculum design system. In our view, an inward-looking policy, and a defensive stance towards this movement (which is strongly represented at the European level through statements, documents and even practices that have resulted in analysis and reflection reports) may foster a disadvantageous isolationism and lessen the institutional visibility of Romanian higher education institutions, which the overall system and the various institutions in particular will not be able to afford. On the other hand, the loss of contact with the labour market, which these curricular tools can strongly facilitate, in the most active and profound way, would go against the developments associated with the idea of *universities without walls*.

As a result of this scenario, the Romanian higher education system in the European context may open an undesired path towards the Scenario 1 proposal, i.e., the emergence of **a global micro-credentials market**. Such situation may be reached because Romanian universities will no longer be the main provider of educational services as well as services intended to build competences and skills aimed at the professionalization required by the labour market. The positive side, however, may be exactly what the scenarios' author has proposed, that is the bringing together through a process of pseudo-consortialization of private sector providers and actors, thus establishing "mega-universities" that may grow into substitutes of classic universities. This can lead to the provision of training content based on micro-credentials. The providers of this kind of content will no longer be controlled by universities which, thankfully, will still share with them areas of this market.

It is true that, given that at national level, universities are criticised for a certain lack of curricular flexibility and their predominantly academic and theoretical orientation, on the one hand, and also knowing the fact that the training programmes market has grown considerably in a structured and formalized manner, on the other hand, aggregating the relevant actors / providers may prove to be a strong non-academic competition.

On the other hand, still, the last scenario described above, i.e., **Scenario 6**, through its conception and layout, signals a potential educational injustice which, we think, the Romanian educational system cannot afford. The differentiation existing on the global / European higher education market, highly polarised along the West-East axis, as well as inciting "consumer" behaviour for "imported" higher education by resorting to academic micro-programmes employing micro-credentials in their curricular layout, cannot make for a balanced and sustainable option. Micro-credentials are tools that may transform the Romanian educational system and its actors into academic training and lifelong learning providers, not in simple users and beneficiaries.

Therefore, for Romania, we think that **the second scenario**, and, why not, **the third**, may lead to an understanding and **broad acceptance of micro-credentials within European University Consortia – European Alliances**, able to design and provide specialised academic / professional content in various international languages, using micro-credentials so as to offer "flexible joint certifications." They will give students the freedom and flexibility of complex learning experiences as they will be able to choose flexible / alternative paths and a mix of European specialisations agreed upon at the level of the above-mentioned alliances. The academic layout underpinned by recognized curricular structures, such as micro-programmes, micro-masters, short courses, short-term intensive programmes, nano-certifications, digital badges, will be recognized by European higher education institutions and employers from the European labour market.

The positive premise of this scenario is the fact that Romania already has 10 universities in European Alliances (three in the first wave³ and seven in the second⁴), with a strong character of diversity and cultural and academic multiplicity. There is also the strong argument that the Romanian State provides constant strategic support, by means of co-funding through the Ministry of Education, for the participation in these projects.

ROMANIAN UNIVERSITIES IN EUROPEAN ALLIANCES	
<i>Universities accepted after the first call (June 2019)</i>	
UNIVERSITY	EUROPEAN ALLIANCE
University of Bucharest	CIVIS, a European Civic University
National University of Political Studies and Public Administration	CIVICA – The European University in social sciences
Technical University of Civil Engineering Bucharest	European University for Smart Urban Coastal Sustainability (CONEXUS)
<i>Universities accepted after the second call (July 2020)</i>	
UNIVERSITY	EUROPEAN ALLIANCE
Politehnica University of Timișoara	Engaged and Entrepreneurial European University as Driver for European Smart and Sustainable Regions (E ³ UDRES ²)
Alexandru Ioan Cuza University of Iași	European Campus of City-Universities (EC2U)
Politehnica University of Bucharest	European Engineering Learning Innovation and Science Alliance (EELISA)
University of Petroșani	The European University Alliance on Responsible Consumption and Production (EURECA-PRO)
Technical University of Cluj-Napoca	European University of Technology (Eut)
Iuliu Hațieganu University of Medicine and Pharmacy Cluj-Napoca	European University of Brain and Technology (NeurotechEU)
West University of Timișoara	UNITA – Universitas Montium

We believe, however, that its strength would be much diminished if we did not take into account **the third scenario** as well, which **puts micro-credentials in the context of lifelong micro-learning**, that is lifelong learning. That is because certification processes, at the junction between higher education proper and ongoing professional training, become ever more blurred. But here is where the new strategy of universities comes in, which in the near

³ https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/IP_19_3389

⁴ https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/ip_20_1264

future could add value to the combination of these two formative educational qualities of Romanian universities, as ongoing processes. Higher education institutions could thus become increasingly interested in professional life cycles and take into consideration multiannual learning contracts with employers and students to provide ongoing professional training and development programmes based on micro-credentials.

Obviously, we must consider the privileged status of **universities as quality guarantors**. Universities are becoming hubs for an array of training programmes built together with relevant labour market actors, nongovernmental or international organizations, thus turning into not only their privileged representatives, but also sustainable providers of trust.

It is probably at this level that the envisaged mechanisms for quality assurance of services based on micro-credentials must be looked at, either through external evaluation performed by a European agency included in the dedicated register (for instance, the Erasmus+ DEQAR-CONNECT project⁵), or through institutional accountability mechanisms, guaranteed by means of the application of procedures complying with the European principles and practices in use at the time of their launch.

An important observation must be made here: **the implementation of academic programmes** (such as micro-programmes) designed on the basis of micro-credentials **must strengthen the autonomy of European universities** (both within and outside alliances), so as they gain force, personality and sustainability in order for them to be able to define their most prominent civic goals, in accord with the dynamics of deep, authentic and durable learning processes, and not to transform them through an ultra-normativised regulatory institutional approach.

The idea of synchronicity of European developments regarding micro-credentials, the depth of understanding, the speed of implementation of some policies, but also the flexibility with which they will produce current academic practices, will make the difference on the global / European higher education market, highly polarised along the East-West axis (referred to above, in the analysis of Scenario 6). This will spur the transformation of the “consumer” behaviour for “imported” higher education by creating authentic providers of programmes built on micro-credentials, not fearing the European competition based on fair, just and sustainable competition. The fear of competition, an old social-psychological issue for the Romanian public sector (analysed in depth by Professor Adrian Miroiu in his famous work entitled exactly ‘The fear of competition’) may be overcome through the motivational benefits engendered by the success of the European Alliances we are part of, providing trust and support.

⁵ <https://www.eqar.eu/kb/projects/deqar-connect/>

4. A possible institutional vision – the experience of the University of Bucharest within the CIVIS European Alliance. Ways into the future...

Yet another possible scenario for the future of micro-credentials in the European academic area, and a scenario that does not seem to have been considered by Camilleri in his analysis, refers to the design of a correlative system centred on **a special link between micro-programmes** in the current, pandemic and post-pandemic, context, and **virtual mobilities**. To keep a symmetry with the previous chapter’s structure and content, we drafted and propose the present chapter as a sketch for a possible institutional vision by bringing to the fore the experience of the University of Bucharest within the CIVIS European Alliance. It is this very experience in the form of a committed and assumed relationship at the institutional level from the part of the CIVIS team of the University of Bucharest that created a correlative solution, i.e., Micro-Credentials & Virtual Mobilities, featuring a high level of uniqueness within the European landscape.

Virtual mobility has sprung from the need to complement physical mobilities, and, in time, turned into one of the pillars of increased collaboration between higher education institutions. Moreover, the new Erasmus+ programme include virtual mobility as a form of mobility in its own right. As noted in Key Action 2, one of the significant elements of the new Erasmus+ programme is “least 50% of the students within the alliance should benefit from such mobility, be it physical, virtual or blended” (European Commission, 2020b, p. 132).

In the European students’ understanding of such form of mobility, renamed “digitally enhanced mobility” (Gaebel et al., 2021; EHEA, 2020), the most important element is not the way a mobility takes place (as one might think), but first and foremost the benefits and opportunities it offers, certainly insofar as micro-credentials and innovative pedagogies are combined gradually and coherently.

This was the premise through which the University of Bucharest defended its proposal for a unique design at the European level for micro-credentials correlated with virtual mobilities and innovative pedagogies. Starting from good practice examples already encountered in Europe and in order to provide multiple opportunities for building flexible educational pathways for the students within the CIVIS European Alliance, a framework for the design of study micro-programmes at the level of partner universities within the Alliance has been created. This framework is based on micro-credentials, micro-certification, virtual mobility, and innovative pedagogies.

Recognized through the ECTS credit points (programmes are allocated 2 to 15 ECTS credit points, based on the required workload, in accordance with the recommendations in the ECTS Users’ Guide⁶) and European certifications (the CIVIS Passport, as a tool for the collection and

⁶ <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/da7467e6-8450-11e5-b8b7-01aa75ed71a1>

portability of CIVIS micro-credentials), the proposed micro-programmes are the ideal context for the design of flexible educational pathways, personalized by the students themselves.

Thus, five learning opportunities based on virtual mobilities and micro-credentials (see Figure 3) have been identified. They can be implemented within the CIVIS University and even extended to and adopted by other Romanian higher education institutions.

Figure 3. Learning opportunities based on virtual mobilities and micro-credentials within the CIVIS University

Building these types of programmes starts precisely from the key characteristics of micro-credentials, described in the second part of this document. Increased transparency, clarity and flexibility have been mentioned as the most important elements for a successful micro-certification.

Figure 4. Components of the CIVIS Micro-credentials design

In this respect, the typology in question has seven major components (see Figure 4), which, on the one hand, places them within the larger spectrum of micro-certifications, as it is now understood within the European area, and, on the other hand, gives them the novel feature of tailored and concrete applicability within an European Alliance, and, if adapted, even for all higher education institutions in Romania.

Besides providing educational components certified via micro-credentials, thus constituting a framework for the design of flexible and tailored learning pathways, the potential of this approach goes even further, in the sense in which these programmes allow all the three major types of education (formal, non-formal and informal) to work together in a balanced manner. Furthermore, it gives the possibility for the learning experience to be recognised transversally, for all the three types.

Using micro-credentials and attaching them to an increasing number of learning opportunities leads to the certification and valorisation of all learning experiences in a visible and recognised manner, so that formal education benefits from non-formal and informal learning experiences. Moreover, it is only this approach that can strengthen the knowledge society in a way that multiple learning experiences are components of an individual’s skills profile.

It is a process of the kind described above that turns certified, recognized, flexible, portable, and personalised learning experiences into real and constant lifelong learning practices, as an individual has learning experiences triggered by the acquisition of knowledge as well as the formation of skills and attitudes. Even if, at first glance, learning is transferred from institutions to individuals, the harmonisation of universities over such perspective makes the individual, who needs and uses learning and education, to go to universities not only to graduate a bachelor’s, master’s, or doctoral programme, but also to gain a more varied array of learning experiences that contributes to them being more and better prepared for their current and constantly changing personal, societal and professional needs.

5. A possible strategic vision for defining a coherent and articulated system for the implementation of micro-credentials in the Romanian higher education system

The future of micro-credentials in the European area ceased to be just a progressive thought entertained by education scholars. It has become a major topic at the highest levels. Thus, Romania has the chance to timely align itself to the trend or just wait until the need to adopt the micro-credentials practice turns into an emergency that needs to be dealt with for compliance reasons. We strongly believe that we do have the necessary resources so that decision makers and stakeholders in Romania can start working on this project, for us not to be caught unprepared by the wide adoption of this certification system.

Below are some requirements for an academic vision that meets the Bologna Process Key Commitments:

- Modular design
- Pluridisciplinarity / Transdisciplinarity
- Academic study credit points: micro-credentials through the ECTS system
- Flexible learning pathways – adaptable and personalised European curriculum, with embedded mobility, leading to European certification
- Multiple ways of implementation: physical / online / blended
- Physical mobility and virtual mobility
- Innovative pedagogies (being recommended to make use of University of Bucharest's validated experience within CIVIS)
- Recognition and certification – the European Student Card Initiative
- Enhanced inter-university cooperation through long-term joint strategies
- Structural, systemic, and sustainable impact

It is worth mentioning the very robust potential to adapt to the European trend and, moreover, the possibility to take concrete steps in a targeted manner making the Romanian higher education system a successful example of modernization in the sense of curricular overhaul and adopting new certification systems. At the end of the day, being so much aware of the requirements that ensure the European modernisation of the higher education system in Romania, it is imperative that we steer our strategic thinking and action along these lines. The year 2021 is dedicated, in the entire European bloc, to discussions, debates and consultations on the topic of micro-credentials for higher education. Then, at the end of the same year, we will have a proposal by the European Commission for a European Council Recommendation, scheduled for December 2021 (European Commission, 2020a, p. 15).

Furthermore, along with these actions taking place at the highest levels, it is more than obvious that the resulted conclusions and concepts should be inserted within the Bologna Process, to create strong synergies by means of specialised operational structures. This is a comprehensive process to be completed by the time the future Communiqué of the Ministerial Conference of the Bologna Process in 2024 will be issued. What will happen meanwhile in the Romanian higher education area will depend much on awareness of decision makers and stakeholders, public or private entities, of the importance of adopting micro-credentials and the curricular reform, so they will not be ivory tower representatives, as described in the above Scenario 5.

In this respect, in order to have a clearer image of an action plan at the macro-systemic level based on which to structure specific actions and targeted educational policies, we have identified certain directions of action for each decision maker in the field of education, to be implemented for the purposes of the present analysis: the Ministry of Education, the National Authority for Qualifications, the Romanian Agency for Quality Assurance in Higher Education

(ARACIS), the Executive Agency for Higher Education, Research, Development, and Innovation Funding (UEFISCDI), and the higher education institutions that are members of European University Alliances (listed above).

Ministry of Education

- Organising a national consultation on the possibility of introducing micro-credentials into the higher education system, involving both decision-makers with direct responsibility over this process, and, especially, education experts, representatives of higher education institutions and actors in the world of work.
- Laying out strategic and educational policy guidelines to facilitate the adjustment of the legal and operational frameworks to allow for the adoption of micro-credentials into the Romanian higher education system, based on the input of experts and stakeholders, in a manner that seeks to anticipate European developments.
- Supporting the introduction of pilot micro-study programmes to analyse their impact and relevance to the development and modernisation of higher education.
- Exploring various possibilities for financing the specific activities to be carried out for the adoption of micro-credentials into the Romanian higher education system.

National Authority for Qualifications

- Analysing the possibility of integrating micro-credentials and micro-certifications into the National Qualifications Framework, with this framework becoming a point of reference for the reshaping of the European Qualifications Framework.
- Initiating discussions with the main actors in the world of work with the aim of reconfiguring qualifications through the adoption of micro-credentials as a means of providing retraining and refresher training for employees.
- Developing a National Register for Higher Education Micro-Credentials, as part of the National Register of Qualifications (RNC), with the objective of providing a unified database that will cover all new education and training programmes built around micro-credentials, while excluding traditional study programmes that are covered by the National Register of Qualifications in Higher Education.
- Preparing a guidance document to assist in the process of adapting the ECTS credit system, in the form of micro-credentials and micro-certifications, to the Romanian higher education system.

Romanian Agency for Quality Assurance in Higher Education

- Exploring potential ways of adapting the tools employed for higher education quality assurance to the new study programmes based on micro-credentials, in line with similar initiatives across Europe.
- Formulating methodologies to help adjust the quality assurance measures used in the Romanian higher education system to allow for the adoption of the new, flexible curricular constructs, as represented by micro-study programmes, micro-certifications, and micro-credentials.

- Integrating micro-credentials into the internal quality assurance processes used in higher education, with the aim of including them in the academic curriculum, by resorting to flexibly designed indicators and methodologies.
- Developing accreditation and evaluation methodologies for micro-study programmes with the aim of fostering institutional and systemic efforts to modernise the curriculum, university autonomy, as well as the flexibilization of academic educational pathways.

Executive Agency for Higher Education, Research, Development, and Innovation Funding

- Adjusting the Educational Integrated Register (REI) and the Unique Student Register (RMU) to enable the integration of higher education micro-credentials into the individual learning pathways of the students and graduates.
- Developing an integrated stocking, portability and sharing system for micro-credentials, accessible to the holder, in the form of a digital portfolio of higher education micro-credentials, in line with similar digital instruments across Europe (such as the Credentify or Europass platforms).
- Linking the REI and RMU with the RNC to ensure interoperability and the ability to give the user access to his or her own educational and professional path, while also attaching portability instruments such as the European Student Card or mobile applications for sharing one's personal educational portfolio.

Universities member of European University Alliances

- Creating working groups with representatives of all the 10 Romanian universities, members of European Alliances, for drawing up joint documents for uniform positioning regarding academic curricular reforms based on micro-credentials.
- Strengthening inter-institutional partnerships by producing joint strategies, projects, documents, and research on the topic of academic curriculum reform through the adoption of micro-credentials and micro-certifications.
- Building joint study micro-programmes for all study levels by at least two universities meant to facilitate the academic mobility (physical, virtual, blended) of students and to foster a richer Romanian academic offer on the international micro-credentials market.
- Producing joint methodologies for the automatic recognition of learning acknowledged through micro-credentials and micro-certifications between universities.

We believe that the proposed strategic directions may be a strong starting point for any educational policy action intended for the adoption and integration of micro-credentials and micro-certifications within the Romanian higher education system.

Worded in a targeted manner and addressed explicitly to decision makers responsible for various components that make up the entire mechanism of the higher education system in Romania, these strategic directions may be necessary steps offering an extra chance to position the Romanian higher education system in a privileged place, along with the greatest European and global education actors, in the midst of a comprehensive academic curricular overhaul taking place worldwide.

Of course, we can opt to wait for external prompts (which usually reach us when there is little contribution that we can make) or we can act on global modern curricular emulations, so that we will be starting a comprehensive academic curricular overhaul by adopting and integrating micro-credentials into the Romanian higher education system.

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As mentioned in Chapter 4 above, to create a favourable environment for the development of micro-programmes within the European University Alliances, efforts have been made to build an implementation framework for virtual mobilities within the CIVIS Alliance. These mobilities are designed to tie into micro-credentials and micro-certifications as an overall concept within the European landscape. The University of Bucharest’s experience as member of a European Alliance gives credibility to the successful adoption of micro-credentials by the higher education system in Romania.

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